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Buen Vivir (living well) in Ecuador: Community and environmental satisfaction without household material prosperity?

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Abstract

This paper provides a quantitative approach to assessing whether the subjective wellbeing (SWB) of Ecuadorian people is dependent on income and employment or on more distinctive features relating to *Buen Vivir* ethos. The latter are reflected in the indigenous *Buen Vivir* ideology, based mainly on relations with the community, the environment and food sovereignty. The empirical analysis shows that both *Buen Vivir* features and factors such as income and unemployment status are significant in the models explaining SWB. Accordingly, economic policies should take into account the *Buen Vivir* ethos, that seems to be important for the SWB of the Ecuadorian people. This supports the conservationist political position, which focuses on protecting the environment and people's traditional livelihoods, rather than the extractive view, which regards people's welfare as merely dependent on income.

Keywords: Subjective wellbeing Economic policies, Environmental protection, Community, Food sovereignty, Buen Vivir

1. Introduction

Buen Vivir (*suma qamaña* in Aymara, *sumak kawsay* in Quichua, *ñandareko* in Guaraní, *küme mongen* in Mapuche, and *living well* in English) is a cultural concept of wellbeing that emerged in Latin America in the early 2000s, when the indigenous movement became a major social and political actor in Ecuador and Bolivia (Torrez, 2001; Viteri Gualinga, 2002; Yampara, 2001). Related academic discussion followed (late 2000s), and considerable research has since been carried out on this issue. As a result, *Buen Vivir* has become an increasingly international subject (Correa, 2012; Escobar, 2010; Farah and Vasapollo, 2011; Gudynas, 2011a; Mejido Costoya, 2013; Radcliffe, 2012; Vanhulst and Beling, 2014; Walsh, 2010).

The philosophy of *Buen Vivir* is based on the indigenous conception that nature, community and individuals all share the same material and spiritual dimensions (Gudynas and Acosta, 2011; Guillén and Phélan, 2012; Tortosa, 2012). The community as a whole is more important

than the individuals within it, and community life enables individuals to develop their abilities and enrich their knowledge without endangering human health and the environment. In addition, human beings are considered part of nature and their quality of life depends on all the living and non-living elements with which they share the planet. Nature (*Pachamama* in the indigenous traditions) is seen as an integrated whole in which human beings are interrelated with the environment, and has intrinsic value, regardless of any benefits for humans (Huanacuni, 2010; Pacari, 2008). Human beings belong to nature, not vice-versa, and every environmental damage has a negative impact on human life. Environmental protection is based on reciprocity between nature, the community and its individuals (Medina, 2001; Temple, 2001), and active participation in community spaces and local institutions is essential in order to achieve *Buen Vivir* (Macas, 2010).¹

¹ In this paper, we use the expressions *Buen Vivir* ethos, *Buen Vivir* philosophy, *Buen Vivir* ideology or *Buen Vivir* features to refer to this original *Buen Vivir* that has grown from indigenous traditions: harmonious coexistence with nature, power-sharing relationships and collective rights, sense of community, and local and primary production of food in a community's own territory for self-consumption. A compilation of texts on *Buen Vivir* philosophy in the indigenous tradition can be found in Hidalgo Capitán et al. (2014).

In Ecuador, *Buen Vivir* appeared in the political debate at the Constituent Assembly (2007–2008), and the concept was eventually included in its Constitution (Ecuador Constitution, 2008).² In the process of designing the Constitution, *Buen Vivir* was discussed by different actors in the society, aiming to reflect the Ecuadorian people's ethos regarding what defines a good life. There is no clear conceptualization of *Buen Vivir* in the Ecuadorian Constitution, however a vague definition of the concept can be drawn from it: '*Buen Vivir* as a way of life in harmony with nature and community' (Ecuador Constitution, 2008:15). Although several academics and policymakers may be in agreement as to the above definition (Hidalgo-Capitán and Cubillo-Guevara, 2013), *Buen Vivir* is still a polysemous concept that is subject to different definitions and interpretations, depending on its aims, uses or theoretical framework, among others.³

The analysis and study of *Buen Vivir* is very complex and can be approached through two interrelated and complementary discussions: firstly, the conceptual and theoretical approach, and secondly, the political practice. This paper focuses on the second, that is, the open discussion in the political arena on how to maintain people's *Buen Vivir* in Ecuador (Acosta and Martínez, 2009; Correa, 2013a; Cuví et al., 2013; Gudynas, 2011a; Houtart, 2011). This discussion influences policies and interpretations of 'what people need to achieve *Buen Vivir*'. From the various interpretations of this issue, two extremely different political views can be observed. Firstly, the extractive position, which views natural resources as tools for achieving *Buen Vivir*, and secondly, the conservationist position, which emphasises respect for nature and community relations as ways of maintaining *Buen Vivir*.

The extractive view is commonly known as 'republican biosocialism', 'twenty-first-century socialism' or '*Buen Vivir* socialism', and reflects the government position (Coraggio, 2007; Falconí and Muñoz, 2012; Páez, 2010; Ramírez Gallegos, 2010; SENPLADES, 2010, 2013).⁴ The conservationist view is prominent in the indigenous movements—through platforms such as the Confederation of Indigenous Nations from Ecuador, (CONAIE) and the Confederation of Kichua Nations of Ecuador (ECUARUNARI)—some opposition political parties—such as the People's Democratic Movement (MPD) and the Pachakutik political party (MUPP)⁵—and some progressive and critical intellectual circles in Ecuador and beyond (Acosta, 2012; Dávalos, 2008; Gudynas, 2013a; Oviedo, 2011; Quijano, 2011; Tortosa, 2012; Vega, 2012).

According to the extractivists, the first step to take in order to achieve *Buen Vivir* is eliminating income poverty and unemployment as soon as possible. A progressive process of endogenous development is necessary in order to improve the wellbeing of the people of Ecuador. This process must achieve energy sovereignty, food sovereignty and financial sovereignty in the medium and long term (16–20 years) (SENPLADES, 2009). Extractivists argue that Ecuador is still at an early stage, a build-up phase which requires the promotion and creation of jobs in the production sector to guarantee basic needs, including food-related

needs. In this stage, income from the extraction of raw materials is important in order to substantially reduce the zones of poverty and social exclusion affecting many areas of Ecuador (SENPLADES, 2007, 2009, 2013). The policy strategy involves exploiting natural resources in the country, above all copper, gas and oil, and assigning the benefits to the local community via employment generation and fiscal income distribution (Correa, 2013a,b; SENPLADES, 2013). Therefore, the extractivists believe that material prosperity should be an *ex ante* requisite to guarantee *Buen Vivir*. This political interpretation of *Buen Vivir* is based on a traditional conception of wellbeing linked to increased material prosperity and employment creation.

The conservationist view takes a critical position towards the extractive vision. According to conservationists, the extractive position, which they call 'neo-progressive extractivism', 'neo-extractivism' or 'brown socialism', seeks *Buen Vivir* through a model of production and mass consumption and goes against the essence of the *Buen Vivir* definition (Acosta, 2012; Escobar, 2010; Gudynas, 2010, 2011b; Tortosa, 2009).⁶ Extractivism maintains a conventional emphasis on economic growth, fostering the massive extraction of natural resources as a primary means to guarantee *Buen Vivir* and casting aside any respect for nature and indigenous communities (Acosta, 2011; Cuví et al., 2013; Gudynas, 2013b). The conservationist view argues that to achieve *Buen Vivir*, it is necessary to transition smoothly from a growth economic model, based largely on depletion of natural resources, to another model that ends poverty while enhancing social inclusion, environmental protection and community building.⁷ According to the conservationist position, the extractive strategy is illogical and directly contradicts the *Buen Vivir* philosophy because it is guided by a productivist vision of wellbeing (Gudynas, 2010). However, the extractivists believe that there is no inconsistency in their position, their defence being that income and employment are essential prerequisites to guarantee *Buen Vivir* (Falconí and Muñoz, 2012; SENPLADES, 2010).

These two political interpretations have been extensively discussed, and an empirical analysis that identifies the determinants of the Ecuadorian people's quality of life could shed light on the current discussion. Within this context, the aim of this paper is to implement this analysis by taking a subjective wellbeing (SWB) approach that may support either the extractivist or the conservationist political position as to how to maintain *Buen Vivir*.⁸ To achieve this objective, we use a representative sample of two Ecuadorian cantons comprising 1174 rural households. In order to scientifically support some of the arguments of each view, we relate the life satisfaction of individuals to domains and variables connected to the *Buen Vivir* ethos; particularly community, environment, and food sovereignty, as well as variables and domains related to material aspects such as income and unemployment status. In this vein, a significant influence of aspects such as

⁶ For a more in-depth analysis of the distinction between 'extractivism' and 'neo-extractivism' see Gudynas (2011b, 2012) and Vanhulst and Beling (2014).

⁷ Some of the proposals of the conservationist view are: to link specific actions to specific territories, to take better account of environmental and social costs when calculating extraction costs, to reduce energy and materials consumption, to impose a severance tax on extraction of natural sources, redefining the notion of social, economic and ecological justice, and to put the emphasis on the use of and access to goods and services, rather than on ownership. For more information on these proposals see Acosta et al. (2013), Almeida (2012) and Gudynas and Alayza (2012).

⁸ There are different interpretations and definitions of SWB used in the literature (Diener et al., 1999). In this paper we put life satisfaction and satisfaction regarding several other domains under the umbrella concept of SWB, taken to be synonymous with happiness. Using life satisfaction as a proxy of the quality of life of the Ecuadorian people allows us to centre the discussion on the individuals themselves rather than impute or presume what makes them satisfied (Rojas, in press), and to avoid the assumption that certain drivers could either improve or impair their wellbeing. As *Buen Vivir* concepts are defined by the people and are for the people, the use of SWB as a proxy of the quality of life of Ecuadorians can serve as an empirical basis to orientate policies to guarantee the *Buen Vivir* of the population. For further discussion on the usefulness of SWB measures to avoid presumption and imputation of the drivers of people's quality of life see Rojas (in press), and for the usefulness of those measures in order to proxy *Buen Vivir* see Guardiola (2011).

² In Bolivia, the *Buen Vivir* concept (or *Vivir Bien* as those in the region prefer to call it) is also included in the debate at the Constituent Assembly (2006–2009) and in Bolivia's new Constitution (2009). This paper focuses on Ecuador; for a specific analysis of the Bolivian case see Farah and Vasapallo (2011) and Mejido Costoya (2013). For an illustration of the differences in the treatment of *Buen Vivir* in both Constitutions see Gudynas (2011a).

³ Some authors have made an effort to analyse, summarise and classify the different theoretical interpretations of and discussions about *Buen Vivir*. See Gudynas (2012), Hidalgo-Capitán (2012), Hidalgo-Capitán and Cubillo-Guevara (2013), Houtart (2011) and Tortosa (2012). Within this context, Vanhulst and Beling (2014) argue that taking into account the open debate on the definition of *Buen Vivir*, it is difficult to establish a precise definition including all aspects and reflecting the complexity of the *Buen Vivir* ethos. There is also criticism of the extent which the *Buen Vivir* term is subject to particular interpretations from the political powers in order to achieve their particular objectives (Tortosa, 2012) and even about the appropriation of this concept from the indigenous population, transforming it into a different one from the government interpretation (Oviedo, 2011).

⁴ SENPLADES is the Spanish acronym for the National Secretariat for Development and Planning in Ecuador (*Secretaría Nacional de Planificación y Desarrollo*).

⁵ These two parties, jointly with other parties and some social movements (CONAIE and ECUARUNARI among others) make up the Plurinational Unity Movement of the Lefts, a political coalition founded in 2011.

income and employment, and a non-significant influence of *Buen Vivir* features on the life satisfaction of Ecuadorians would support the extractive view, while the contrary would back a conservationist view. In addition, the results allow us to assess the effect of *Buen Vivir*-related factors on SWB.⁹

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a theoretical framework of the SWB literature that establishes a benchmark for interpreting the results. We were motivated by the literature on SWB to try to determine which political alternative could more successfully improve the quality of life of the Ecuadorian people. In Section 3 we explain the study area, the data and the variables used in this study, while Section 4 includes the analysis of the data and interprets the results. Finally, in Section 5 we discuss and make policy recommendations, and in Section 6 we conclude.

2. A SWB Theoretical Framework

An important branch of SWB studies interprets happiness as an ultimate aim and has attempted to identify the drivers of happiness in order to inform public policy. In this section we aim to draw on the SWB literature to find theories that could support both *Buen Vivir* political positions: the extractive and the conservationist. Firstly, we deal with the extractivist positions. Secondly, we centre on the conservationist. These theories serve as a framework for the results in the empirical analysis.

Concerning the extractivist position, there is ample research, particularly in economics, that studies the effect of personal income and unemployment on SWB. Empirical results suggest that the influence of income on SWB follows a log scale. This has significant implications for poor people, as an increase in income would increase their happiness assessment much more than for wealthier people (Dolan et al., 2008; Graham and Pettinato, 2001). It is assumed that people with higher incomes have more opportunities to satisfy their needs and desires, particularly through the markets. Greater status is accorded to having a higher income, thus income has an effect on SWB not only in absolute terms but also in relation to other people's income. In this sense, therefore, people compare themselves with groups of their peers in order to determine their SWB (Layard, 2005). Some research argues that there is a threshold above which income brings greater SWB and beyond which the additional gains of an increase in income are considerably lower (Borghesi and Vercelli, 2011). When income is low, an increase can permit people to buy essential commodities, such as food and shelter, or collectively fund improved access to water and sanitation facilities. Employment status itself is also related to SWB: being unemployed can cause depression and stress, and can also result in social stigma, lowering SWB (Dolan et al., 2008; Frey and Stutzer, 2002).

The usefulness of income and the ability to transform it into goods and services that satisfy primary needs is consistent with Abraham Maslow's (1943) basic needs approach, which argues that to have a good life, a minimum material achievement is necessary as a prerequisite for higher aspirations. The greater the income, the higher the number of opportunities to satisfy the physiological and safety needs of a person and the greater the possibility of satisfying higher-ranked needs such as belonging and self-actualization. All this evidence supports political initiatives that aim to generate income and create employment for the people. This is in line with the Ecuadorian Government's extractive view that natural resources should first be used to eradicate hunger and poverty (Correa, 2012, 2013a,b). Accordingly, people should take advantage of resources in order to guarantee their material prosperity before any other consideration; such reasoning supports an extractive viewpoint.

However, some clarifications should be made in support of other views such as the conservationist view. Firstly, the influence of income on SWB is influenced by different outlooks on life. That is, individuals differ in their notions of the definition of a good life, and according to their particular *Buen Vivir* ethos, the influence of income on their SWB can differ. In this vein, Rojas (2007) shows for a sample of Mexicans, that depending on each person's personal attitude to life, income can be an important explanatory variable for some people, while for others it can be completely irrelevant. Secondly, there can be other ways to satisfy needs apart from income and market interactions. For instance, subsistence agriculture and goods exchange can also satisfy material needs, substituting income. Subsistence agriculture and self-sufficiency can be important livelihoods that permit the satisfaction of several needs, not only in material terms, such as avoiding hunger, but also in non-material terms as a sustainable way of life. They can also be a source of self-employment. Thirdly, other variables unrelated to income can also increase or decrease SWB. In fact, regression analysis shows that the income-SWB relation is weak (Kingdon and Knight, 2006; Rojas, 2008), which leaves room for other explanations of happiness such as leisure, health and free time. Similarly, in Latin America there is evidence of several groups of people in rural areas having high values of SWB even though they live in disadvantaged circumstances. In the case of the Mexican Mayans, Guardiola et al. (2012) argues that spirituality and religion may play a non-material part in increasing SWB. In the Peruvian case, it has been shown that the lack of comparison with rich people results in a high level of SWB (Guillen-Royo and Velazco, 2012).

Therefore, people's lives include other dimensions beyond income and material aspects.¹⁰ Aiming to take into account the many dimensions of life, the domains of life approach holds that life satisfaction is related to a general construct involving the satisfaction of specific life domains. Domains of life have traditionally been viewed as the satisfaction that an individual experiences in a particular dimension of life, such as health, working environment or leisure (Cummins, 1996). Domains related to environment and community participation are particularly relevant in our analysis because, as mentioned in the introduction, nature and community are key aspects of the *Buen Vivir* philosophy. Some evidence in Mexico suggests that achievement in several life domains such as leisure time and family ties may explain some people's life satisfaction in spite of living in income poverty (Rojas, 2008). This situation could also be relevant to community participation and environment domains. Community participation is commonly found to be positively associated with SWB in most studies (Dolan et al., 2008). Analyzing 49 countries, Helliwell (2003) found that people involved in a community organisation were more satisfied than those that were not affiliated. The involvement in church activities is also found by Helliwell (2003) to be linked to life satisfaction, even when controlled by religious convictions. Therefore it can be said that connections between people and the interaction of people within the community generally increase SWB.

In comparison to income-SWB research, the literature addressing environment-SWB is relatively scarce but expanding. Environmental degradation has been empirically associated with lower SWB in many countries (Di Tella and MacCulloch, 2008; Welsch, 2002). Negative implications were also found for a longitudinal study in Germany regarding the influence of concern about pollution on SWB, while a positive influence is found when individuals show concern about biodiversity or interaction with plants and wildlife (Ferrer-i-Carbonell and

⁹ Ramirez Gallegos (2011) used a happiness measure as a proxy of *Buen Vivir* in an Ecuadorian national survey. This paper uses a similar approach to put the results derived from the empirical analysis into a political context.

¹⁰ There are multiple theoretical frameworks that aim to deal with this multidimensionality. A useful recent one is provided by Costanza et al. (2007), which distinguishes four different kinds of capital that permit people to satisfy their many dimensions of life: social capital (networks and norms for cooperative action), human capital (knowledge), built capital (manufactured goods) and natural capital (goods provided by ecosystems). They argue that measuring these dimensions—they refer to them as human needs—requires objective and subjective indicators. In this research we deal with the subjective side via self-reported satisfaction with life and with several life domains.

Gowdy, 2007). The evidence suggests that people's contact with nature is related to a sense of biophilia, creating wellbeing that goes far beyond the use of nature as a production resource. Welsch (2009) provides an explanation of this in the case of pro-environmental consumption. Consumption leads the actor to experience hedonic adaptation associated with extrinsic motivations, while caring for the environment is associated with intrinsic motivations. Intrinsic motivations are related to internal rewards, while extrinsic motivations are more instrumental and materialistic, linked to external material goals. A greater life satisfaction is associated with personalities that are more influenced by intrinsic motivations compared to personalities more focused on pursuing extrinsic goals (Kasser and Ryan, 1996).

3. Study Area, Data and Variables

The field study in this research was carried out in Nabón and Pucará, two cantons in the Jubones River Basin situated in the Azuay Province, in southern Ecuador.¹¹ Nabón has 15,892 inhabitants (46.2% male, 53.8% female), of whom 7.7% live in urban areas and 92.3% in rural areas (INEC, 2010). Pucará has 10,052 inhabitants (48.7% male, 51.3% female), of whom 9.1% live in urban areas and 90.9% in rural areas (INEC, 2010). Both cantons are mainly dedicated to agriculture, with 22.7% of employment in Nabón and 20.1% of employment in Pucará being related to farming. They are two of the poorest cantons in Ecuador; the population living in poverty due to unsatisfied basic needs (UBN) is approximately 65% in both areas.¹²

In this study, our empirical analysis is based on a representative survey conducted in the rural areas of both cantons in November and December 2012. The data were collected by the Public Committee of the Jubones River Basin (*Consortio Público de la Cuenca del Río Jubones* or CCRJ) and by the Program for Population and Sustainable Local Development (*Programa de Población y Desarrollo Local Sustentable* or PYDLOS). All data were collected within the frameworks of the 'Questionnaire Regarding Wellbeing in the Cantons of Nabón and Pucará' (*Encuesta Sobre el bienestar en los cantones de Nabón y Pucará*) and 'Vital Signs of the CCRJ' (*Signos Vitales del CCRJ*) Projects.¹³ The survey consisted of 1174 household interviews in the rural areas in the two cantons (445 in the canton of Pucará and 729 in the canton of Nabón). The sample is representative for the rural area of both cantons.

Before information was collected, a background overview was implemented in order to explore the key issues to be included in the questionnaire. Assemblies were held with rural people in order to help design the questionnaire. A pilot study of 100 households was also implemented. The survey includes information about individuals' self-evaluation of their satisfaction with regards to diverse dimensions of their life (health, security, food security, environmental practice, community life, public investment and so on). The primary new feature that has been implemented compared to other Ecuadorian surveys on this subject such as the 'Employment, Underemployment and Unemployment Survey' (2007, 2008), the 'Annual Labor Survey' (2010, 2011, 2012) or the 'Health, Wellbeing and Ageing Survey'

(2009), is the increased level of detail regarding domain satisfaction and the population SWB as well as the focus on rural areas.

The variables we use from the database are related to SWB, life satisfaction and domain satisfaction, control variables normally used in happiness research, as well as variables related to policy interpretations. We refer to income and employment as variables related to the extractive political view on how to achieve *Buen Vivir*, and variables relating to *Buen Vivir* ethos (environment, community participation and food sovereignty) as more related to the conservationist view. Life satisfaction and domain satisfaction variables were evaluated through a series of questions, starting with the phrase: *How satisfied are you with...?*, followed by '*your life*' or a domain. The answer given was a Likert-type, 1 being very dissatisfied, 5 very satisfied and 3 a mid-point. The different domains were *job, income, free time, family, health, environment* and *community*. The *job* and *income* domains are included to evaluate the importance of the extractive view. In addition, we asked about satisfaction with the *environment* and with *community participation*, which we consider as domains relating to *Buen Vivir* ethos, whose importance could support the conservationist view.

Other data include the employment status of the respondent (1 if *unemployed* and 0 otherwise, from the answer to the question: 'What is your employment status?') and the household per capita income in log terms (*log per capita income*) as variables that are associated with the extractive view. The income variable is calculated by adding up household expenses, savings, debt repayments as well as a market valuation of the self-produced agricultural goods that are consumed by the household.¹⁴

The variables relating to *Buen Vivir* ethos aim to proxy community and environmental involvement. We constructed a *community participation index* by giving values to the different answers to the question: 'To what degree do you participate in different local institutions?' The interviewer read a list of seven possible options¹⁵ in which people could interact and the different possible answers for each were: '*very much*', '*a little*' and '*no participation*'. We gave the value of 1 to '*very much*', 0.5 to '*a little*' and 0 to '*no participation*' for each of the seven variables. We then summed the total of the seven answers for each individual and divided by seven. We used two proxy variables for environmental involvement. Individuals were asked about three different fields that concerned them in an open question.¹⁶ The *environmental concern* variable was equal to 1 if the individual mentioned environment or nature in one of the three replies, and 0 if not. Finally, we proxied the importance of *food sovereignty* in the household by dividing the market value of the food produced in the household by total household expenses. In this variable, we expected to capture not only food sovereignty, but also attachment to and dependence on land as a livelihood. In the same vein, the Ecuadorian Constitution states that people and collectivities should have safe and permanent access to enough nutritive and healthy food, preferably locally-produced in accordance with diverse identities and cultural traditions (Ecuadorian Constitution, Art. 281).

Finally, the socioeconomic variables refer to *age, gender* (1 if the respondent is female and 0 if male), *marriage* (1 if he/she is married and 0 if not), if the respondent can *read and write* (1 if yes and 0 if not).¹⁷

¹¹ In Ecuador there are different levels of administrative division: regions (the coast, the highlands, the Amazon Basin and island territories), provinces (24), cantons (221) and parishes (1228). With 712,127 inhabitants (337,044 men and 375,083 women) Azuay is one of Ecuador's five most densely populated provinces (INEC, 2010). The illiteracy, unemployment and unsatisfied basic needs figures (6.7%, 2.9% and 20.1% respectively) are in line with the national average (6.8%, 4.2% and 26.8%). Azuay and both cantons where the survey was conducted are a hotbed of mining debates. There were some protests last year against prolonged mining activity in the area, although to the best of the author's knowledge, the mining protest has not had an impact on the survey. To support this idea, we observe the reply in our survey to the open question 'what aspects are prioritized for your life'. In the results, no answer mentioned issues connected with the mining debate.

¹² A person is considered to have UBN when they are acutely disadvantaged in terms of health, education, sanitation, nutrition, housing, urban services and job opportunities (Social Indicators System of Ecuador, 2014).

¹³ These projects aim to build a system of identification, systematisation and publication of quality of life indicators.

¹⁴ The value of self consumption is calculated by multiplying the market prices of each crop by the quantity of each crop produced by each household. The market price of each crop was obtained each day during the field work by asking in the local shop or by checking the local market prices in each community.

¹⁵ The different spaces were defined by previous work in the assemblies that were part of the pilot study. These are defined as parish and irrigation boards, cantonal councils, farming organisations, drinking water boards, sports associations and the church.

¹⁶ Specifically, the individuals were asked the following: 'Can you name three areas that concern you?'

¹⁷ The questions included in the questionnaire were: 'How old are you?', 'Are you male or female?', 'What is your marital status?' and 'Are you able to read and write?'

Table 1
Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>life</i>	4.496	0.717	1	5
<i>job</i>	4.286	0.980	1	5
<i>income</i>	3.708	1.028	1	5
<i>free time</i>	4.409	0.947	1	5
<i>family</i>	4.474	0.854	1	5
<i>health</i>	4.089	0.948	1	5
<i>environment</i>	4.423	0.909	1	5
<i>community</i>	4.577	0.723	1	5
<i>age</i>	48.7	18.8	16.0	88.0
<i>gender</i>	0.669		0	1
<i>marriage</i>	0.596		0	1
<i>unemployed</i>	0.024		0	1
<i>read and write</i>	0.144		0	1
<i>log income</i>	4.387	0.588	2.015	6.368
<i>community participation index</i>	0.310	0.229	0	1
<i>environmental concern (%)</i>	0.255		0	1
<i>food sovereignty</i>	0.200		0	1

4. Estimation Strategy and Results

The descriptive statistics of the data are found in Table 1. It is worth highlighting the high life satisfaction average. In fact, more than 60% of people are very satisfied, while only 1.6% of people are very dissatisfied or dissatisfied. Satisfaction in domains related to *Buen Vivir* ethos is also quite high.¹⁸ This could lead to a preliminary conclusion that, despite being disadvantaged, people are quite satisfied, supporting the conservationist view on how to achieve *Buen Vivir*. However, the income satisfaction domain has the lowest average and the highest standard deviation, suggesting differences in the sample and possible reasons to support the extractive solutions.

A more extensive analysis of the variations of life satisfaction is necessary in order to assess the extent to which *Buen Vivir* related features could influence life satisfaction. Concerning life domains, we estimate the following model:

$$life^* = \alpha_1 job + \alpha_2 income + \alpha_3 freetime + \alpha_4 family + \alpha_5 health + \alpha_6 environment + \alpha_7 community + \varepsilon,$$

where ε refers to the error term and α to the estimated coefficients. We estimate an alternative model (1b) that omits the domains related to *Buen Vivir* ethos with the intention of checking for the robustness of the α variables and evaluating the gained explanatory power by introducing these domains. In order to estimate this model we use the ordered probit technique, which approximates the $life^*$ variable using the satisfaction with $life$ variable explained above.

Table 2 displays the results of model 1a and model 1b. All domains are significant and have an estimated positive coefficient. Marginal probabilities of the model 1a that includes the *Buen Vivir* domains are showed in Table 3. The coefficient of the community domain is the highest in the equation. The adjusted R squared is slightly higher in model 1a (0.28) than in model 1b (0.23), which indicates that the *community* and *environment* domains have a relevant but not outstanding correlation with life satisfaction. Community satisfaction displays the greatest coefficient in the estimations, but income and job satisfaction also have a significant effect.

In the previous estimations we took a domain approach to life satisfaction. We made further estimations in order to assess the influence of

Table 2
The influence of *Buen Vivir* domains on life satisfaction.

Variable	Model 1a	Model 1b
<i>job</i>	0.209*** (0.000)	0.254*** (0.000)
<i>income</i>	0.220*** (0.000)	0.219*** (0.000)
<i>free time</i>	0.188*** (0.000)	0.233*** (0.000)
<i>family</i>	0.258*** (0.000)	0.372*** (0.000)
<i>health</i>	0.278*** (0.000)	0.310*** (0.000)
<i>environment</i>	0.216*** (0.000)	
<i>community</i>	0.414*** (0.000)	
Adj R ²	0.2775	0.2351
Chi ² test (p-value)	392.27(0.000)	321.39(0.000)

p-values in brackets. * Significant at 10%, ** significant at 5% and *** significant at 1%.

Table 3
Marginal probabilities of model 1a (from Table 2).

Variable	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither sat. nor dissat.	Satisfied	Very satisfied
<i>job</i>			-0.012	0.068	0.080
<i>income</i>			-0.012	0.071	0.084
<i>free time</i>			-0.011	0.061	0.072
<i>family</i>		-0.001	-0.014	0.084	0.099
<i>health</i>		-0.001	-0.016	0.091	0.107
<i>environment</i>		-0.001	-0.012	0.070	0.083
<i>community</i>		-0.001	-0.023	0.135	0.158

Marginal probabilities for each outcome, computed at the mean. Empty fields indicate a marginal probability not significant at 10%.

the household material related variables and the *Buen Vivir* ethos-related variables in life satisfaction. We again use ordered probit to estimate the following model:

$$life^* = \beta_1 age + \beta_2 gender + \beta_3 marriage + \beta_4 readandwrite + \beta_5 unemployed + \beta_6 logpercapitaincome + \beta_7 communitypaticindex + \beta_8 concernenvironment + \beta_9 foodsovereignty + e.$$

The error term is represented by e and the coefficients by the β s. Three alternative models are also estimated: model 2b includes only socioeconomic variables (excluding income), model 2c adds income to the previous model, and model 2d adds variables relating to *Buen Vivir* ethos to model 2b. Again, alternative models permit the evaluation of robustness and account for variations of explanatory power.¹⁹

The estimations and the marginal probabilities for model 2a are depicted in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. With regards to control variables, the *married* variable is significant in all models and positively relates to the probability of being satisfied or very satisfied. These findings are similar to those in other SWB studies (Dolan et al., 2008) and to the evidence from Ecuador (Ramirez Gallegos, 2011). The variables *age* and *gender* have an unstable significance and *read and write* is found to be non-significant. The income and unemployment variables, as well as the variables relating to *Buen Vivir* ethos, are significant in the two models included. Income and being unemployed correlate with the probability of being satisfied or very satisfied in the expected direction

¹⁸ This is in line with the results found by Ramirez Gallegos (2011). He uses a national sample to estimate that, although happiness is related to income, around 25% of people in the lowest income quintile report that they are happy or very happy. In addition, the domains related to marital status, environment and social relations are the highest-ranked in his research, with the last two domains related to *Buen Vivir* ethos.

¹⁹ We implement a variance inflation factor (VIF) test to account for possible imperfect collinearity. The test indicates that there are no collinearity problems, with a maximum VIF value of 1.35. This disregards possible interactions of the explanatory variables that could affect the results, such as a possible overlapping of environmental concern with economic related variables.

Table 4
The influence of *Buen Vivir* variables on life satisfaction.

Variable	Model 2a	Model 2b	Model 2c	Model 2d
age	-0.006** (0.018)	-0.002 (0.365)	-0.003 (0.189)	-0.004* (0.052)
gender	0.199** (0.019)	0.108 (0.155)	0.124 (0.105)	0.168** (0.043)
marriage	0.253*** (0.002)	0.242*** (0.001)	0.257*** (0.000)	0.232*** (0.004)
unemployed	-0.603*** (0.007)	-0.557*** (0.005)	-0.553*** (0.004)	-0.620*** (0.008)
read and write	-0.013 (0.914)	-0.039 (0.727)	0.016 (0.884)	-0.076 (0.540)
log income	0.254*** (0.000)		0.227*** (0.000)	
commun particip index	0.725*** (0.000)			0.826*** (0.000)
environmental concern	-0.176* (0.064)			-0.163* (0.085)
food sovereignty	2.313*** (0.000)			2.196*** (0.000)
Adj R ²	0.0761	0.0111	0.0182	0.0685
Chi ² test (p-value)	121.84 (0.000)	25.91 (0.000)	39.07 (0.000)	99.54 (0.000)

p-values in brackets. * Significant at 10%, ** significant at 5% and *** significant at 1%.

(Dolan et al., 2008). Participation in the community positively relates to being satisfied or very satisfied, and negatively relates to being dissatisfied or neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. The probability of being very dissatisfied, dissatisfied and neither satisfied nor dissatisfied decreases—and the probability of the other outcomes increases—as *self production* increases. Concern with the environment negatively relates to the probability of being very satisfied or satisfied, in line with the results found by Ferrer-i-Carbonell and Gowdy (2007).

It is worth highlighting that the models explaining life satisfaction by socioeconomic and environmental factors (models 2a and 2d) multiply the value of the adjusted R-squared by more than 3 in comparison to the models that do not include variables related to community and participation (models 2b and 2c). Variables related to *Buen Vivir* ethos are therefore important in explaining the SWB of Ecuadorians in the sample. Nevertheless, income still displays a positive and significant coefficient in the analysis, and unemployment a negative and significant one, which suggests that *Buen Vivir* related variables are not sources of SWB alone.

5. Policy Implications and Discussion

The results in the empirical part of this paper partially support both policy orientations. Income and employment status influence the SWB of the Ecuadorian rural people. However, the variables relating to *Buen*

Table 5
Marginal probabilities of model 2a (from Table 4).

Variable	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither sat. nor dissat.	Satisfied	Very satisfied
age		0.000	0.001	-0.001	-0.002
gender		-0.004	-0.023	0.049	0.077
marriage		-0.005	-0.029	0.062	0.098
unemployed		0.023	0.090	-0.117	-0.237
read and write					
log income		-0.005	-0.028	0.064	0.098
community participation index		-0.015	-0.080	0.182	0.280
concern of environment			0.021	-0.043	-0.069
self production	-0.011	-0.046	-0.254	0.581	0.893

Marginal probabilities for each outcome, computed at the mean. Empty fields indicate a marginal probability not significant at 10%.

Vivir ethos that aim to proxy the *Buen Vivir* concept are also significant in explaining SWB; undermining these variables in policy action could result in a human cost that is reflected in a lower SWB. As conservationists claim, the use of nature as an economic resource contradicts the *Buen Vivir* principles set out in the Constitution. Nature is a subject of law (see the Ecuadorian Constitution, chapter 7) and it is necessary to protect 'the right of the people to live in a healthy and ecologically balanced environment, warranting sustainability and *Buen Vivir* (Art. 14)'. Transforming nature as a means of economic growth could also erode community relations and be detrimental to the community vision of a good life (Acosta, 2012). This reasoning raises important criticisms of the extractive *Buen Vivir* political position that could reduce people's positive interactions with nature, and jeopardize nature itself as well as community relations. Exploitation of nature could therefore increase economic growth and reduce poverty, but at a high cost.

Contrary to this, President Correa has repeatedly publicly stated that his government's environmental policy was necessary 'for the country to emerge from underdevelopment and to attend to the poorest. We cannot live as beggars sitting on a sack of gold' (Correa, 2013a). The results in this research also suggest that conservationist perspectives should be complemented with strategies that improve the economic potential of the Ecuadorian people, as a conservationist approach alone cannot guarantee life satisfaction. *Buen Vivir* policies in the Government require a continuous process of reflective action which ensures it respects the commitments adopted in the Ecuadorian Constitution. Continuous effort in the areas of feedback, research and analysis is necessary to make both views compatible and cover any knowledge gaps.²⁰ The challenge for the political and social actors in the forthcoming agenda should be to find policies that aim to take into account the material and nonmaterial dimensions. The two political views and the two paradigms should be debated in order to find and to follow paths that do not jeopardize environment and community ties.

6. Concluding Remarks

In this paper we aim to quantitatively evaluate the influence of *Buen Vivir* features in the SWB of a sample of rural Ecuadorians households. The results suggest that policy interventions focusing on raising income or *Buen Vivir* dimensions alone will be insufficient. Policies that foster *Buen Vivir* ethos while raising income and employment would succeed; aiming at improving economic potential while preserving people's ties to the community and the land. The importance of *Buen Vivir* ethos variables and domains in explaining life satisfaction contradicts the extractive position, but the significance of variables and domains related to income and employment status does not exclusively support the conservationist political interpretation on how to achieve *Buen Vivir*. In other words, income, employment and increase in income satisfaction are necessary for the Ecuadorian people to be satisfied with their lives. This result is in contrast with the fact that descriptive statistics indicate that people are quite satisfied on average despite living in disadvantaged circumstances. This apparently puzzling conclusion may be explained by the following reasoning: people in the sample are in

general highly satisfied, probably due to issues relating to the *Buen Vivir* ethos,²¹ but material achievements play a role in the differences between individuals. Those conclusions are based on the analysis of a representative sample from two cantons in southern Ecuador, but are not representative of the whole country.

With regards to *Buen Vivir* ethos variables, environmental concern and community participation, as well as environment and community

²⁰ To this end, new indicators are needed in order to capture the complexity of *Buen Vivir*. A discussion on the metrics of *Buen Vivir* can be found in Alaminos (2012), Albó (2010), Phelan (2011) and Phelan and Guillén (2012, 2014).

²¹ Indigenous leaders have suggested that what looks like poverty to the industrialized world may not be regarded as poverty by indigenous people (Viteri Gualinga, 2002). This may reinforce the role of *Buen Vivir* in high self-reported satisfaction.

domains, positively influence life satisfaction. Food sovereignty raises life satisfaction, which supports the conservationist view on attachment to land. The influence of these variables supports the claim that features of certain population groups should be taken into account in economic policies as well as in studies aiming to evaluate the success of such policies in terms of people's lives. Failure to take into account various dimensions of life could misinform policy recommendations that entail human costs.

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